

SOCIAL GOALS OF STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation: During the development of the social sphere, a number of important legal documents, state and regional development programs aimed at the rapid socio-economic development of the country, creation of appropriate conditions for the decent living of our people, as well as realization of the creative power of citizens in the implementation of reforms were adopted. That is why material, labor and financial resources are spent on the development of the social sphere.

Key words: Social infrastructure, economic real sector, socio-political, modernization, social assistance, social sphere, material benefits, scientific research, labor resources, fund, efficiency, modernization, financial resources, social norm.

It is known that the development of any field, specialty, first of all, directly depends on the processes of providing high-quality education. For this reason, increasing the level and content of educational processes formed in the society allows to find a solution to the goal set by the society, that is, personnel training.

In 2017-2021, the fourth direction of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan called "Development of the social sphere" is to increase the employment of the population, social protection of citizens and their health, road - transport , development and modernization of engineering - communication and social infrastructure, improving the supply of electricity and gas to the population, improving the quality of social assistance provided to the needy sections of the population, improving the social and political status of women and girls, reforming the health sector , provides for the convenience of pre-school educational institutions, improving the quality of general secondary education, secondary special and higher education, and implementing measures for their development [1].

The connection between the factor of effective and high-quality organization of higher education and the social goals and values of the student is important in ensuring the quality of personnel. Therefore, we pay special attention to this issue in our sociological research aimed at developing scientific conclusions and recommendations in the higher education system. It should be noted that values are always relevant and important in the social and spiritual life of a person. Therefore, values gain importance by deeply expressing the inner and outer experiences of a person's existence. According to what values each person uses in his activity, what values he strives for, the public opinion about him was formed. After all, it is inevitable that the facets of a person's activity are manifested only in the community, in the social environment.

Social goals also serve as criteria for thinking and organizing activities in people's minds. Social goals serve as a means of meeting material and spiritual needs for society and

individuals. It is very important for what purpose social goals and values are used in practice. A person prefers material and spiritual wealth based on his education and spiritual preparation. In fact, material and spiritual values are inextricably linked and have an impact on human education, complementing each other in terms of content.

Values are also interrelated with the factor of social purpose, and in one respect, the social purpose determines which values it is devoted to. Therefore, values are determined by a person's place in society and their interests. Market economy relations have a direct impact on the value system.

Service areas include public education, higher education, health care, arts and culture, science, physical education and sports, scientific research, public administration, defense, and domestic services. . It is impossible to imagine the development of society without them. Because the general direction of the work of the employees of this field is aimed at the social and spiritual development of man and society. Social infrastructure solves important social tasks related to improving the well-being of the population, improving the working conditions and lifestyle of people, ensures the satisfaction of the needs of the members of the society, and creates conditions for the economic growth of the country. The following are the main tasks of education students in Uzbekistan to further develop the social sphere and ensure the development of social infrastructure:

- shaping the introduction of modern educational standards and innovative teaching methods into the field of education;
- further improvement of the system of social support and encouragement of medical system employees;
- revision of the powers of regional, city and district governments and village councils;
- increase the level of population employment and prevent and reduce unemployment;
- revision of the system of documents and recommendations, normative guidelines regulating the social sphere;
- determination of the tasks and goals of republican, branch and regional management agencies, scope of property rights and determination of powers;
- raising the social protection model to the level of international standards based on real requirements;
- consideration of regional features and factors, focusing on developing a system of social indicators;
- development of works on construction of low-cost houses in rural areas and high-rise buildings in cities on the basis of new model projects, etc. k.

When a person relies on certain valuable situations, first of all, he creates a unique and appropriate worldview of values based on "understanding the values themselves", being able to analyze them, and being able to protect them.

In conclusion, it can be said that the problems of strong social policy in our republic are to raise the development of social goals to the level of the state task, and at the same time to develop the investment policy, regardless of the source of financing, along with all the established advantages of its implementation. requires us to improve our work.

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